

Analyzing The Spatial Distribution Modeling Of Urban Settlements In Anbar Governorate Using Modern Statistical Analysis Methods (Arc Map)

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July 26, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: February 28, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Arc Map, Anbar Governorate, Statistical Analysis Methods</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6308598</p>	<p><i>The aim of the research is to analyze the spatial distribution modeling of human (urban) settlements in Anbar Governorate and to determine the form of its spatial extension, through the use of modern statistical methods related to the study and analysis of these patterns through the available technical capabilities represented by the standard distance and the neighborhood link. The study relied on GIS software represented by the (Arc Map) program based on corrected satellite visuals captured from the American satellite (Quick Bird), with a discriminatory accuracy (0.60 cm) for the year 2010, as the analysis of spatial distribution modeling of urban settlements and their mapping (models) was addressed. Objective, after preparing the geographical database for those layers. The research concluded that urban stability in Anbar Governorate is linked to the relationship of man with his environment, where stability reflects the control of geographical factors (natural and human) to a large extent in the spatial distribution pattern of urban stability centers, in terms of their spread, distribution and sizes, and that the spatial distribution of them has taken multiple forms and according to the control Geographical conditions in that distribution. The study recommended the need to develop a comprehensive database for human settlements and to expand the use of geographic information systems for the parties concerned with the process of planning human settlements.</i></p>

Introduction

The analysis of modeling the spatial distribution of urban settlements in the study area is an important study in the field of planning, as it provides a mathematical basis (quantitative) in the light of which the pattern can be determined and accurately distinguished from other patterns of other distributions. Which has attracted great interest among geographical researchers, and this is evident from what Taylor addressed in the research on the interrelationships in the spatial distribution of phenomena, and this trend was reflected in the branches of physical and human geography.

Research problem :

The process of selecting and determining the research problem is the first step of the scientific research steps, which can be summarized in the following question:

1-Human settlements in Anbar Governorate were organized according to natural factors and human behaviors above its land surface. Is it possible to detect these patterns through the use of statistical analysis methods (standard distance and the nearest neighbor correlation) ?

Research Hypothesis :

The research hypothesis is the initial answer that can answer the research problem, which can be summarized as follows :

1-The difference and disparity in the development potential in Anbar Governorate led to an imbalance in the nature of the distribution of human settlements and economic activities in Anbar Governorate, which requires the restructuring of human settlements and economic, administrative and service activities, which leads to reducing the size of the imbalance and creating opportunities for spatial balance .

Research goal :

The research aims to shed light on the modeling analysis of the characteristics of human urban settlements in Anbar Governorate and the nature of their spatial distribution, and also aims primarily to clarify the geographical distribution of settlements in Anbar Governorate, in order to reveal the factors that led to this distribution .

Study Methodology :

Any study must follow a clear scientific approach. The approach followed by the researcher is the descriptive approach that depends on the study of the phenomenon as it exists in reality through attention as an accurate description as well as the systems approach (inductive-analytical approach) through GIS technology. , starting

with data collection, model preparation, processing and analysis using the (Arc Map) program through the Spatial Analysis package .

Spatial and temporal limits :

The study area is determined by the administrative borders of Anbar Governorate, which is located in the western part of Iraq between latitudes (33 30 and 15 35 degrees) north and longitudes (38 45 and 10 44) east. It is bordered to the north and north-east by the governorates of Nineveh and Salah al-Din, to the east by the governorates of Baghdad and Karbala, and to the south by the Najaf governorate, and with regard to its location in relation to neighboring countries, it borders Syria, Jordan and Saudi Arabia, map .(1)

Its area reached (161913) km², which constituted 37.5% of the total area of Iraq of (434,128) km², which is the largest governorate of the country in area and administratively divided the governorate into eleven districts: (Ramadi, Habbaniyah, Hit, Fallujah, Karma, Al-Amriya Anh, Rawah, Haditha, Al-Rutbah, Al-Qaim) .

As for the temporal limits of the study, the research relied on the estimates of the year (2020) in its study of the characteristics of human settlements in Anbar Governorate

Map (1)
The geographical location of Anbar Governorate, Iraq

Source:

-1Republic of Iraq, Ministry of Water Resources, Directorate of Public Survey, Map of Iraq and Anbar Administrative, 2010, scale (500,000:1).

The importance of studying the geographical distribution of human settlements is manifested by revealing the distributional patterns of those settlements because the shape of the distribution reflects the influence of natural and human factors affecting the characteristics of human settlements and reveals their regional relations and the services they provide to their residents, and geographic information systems techniques and statistical methods were used in this research. In order to highlight its capabilities in modeling the spatial distribution of human settlements and finding spatial relationships and outputting its results in the form of spatial maps after analyzing the metadata; The aim of the analysis was to determine the forms of the distribution and find the spatial relationship to the distribution of these stables, which we will study as follows :

1-Population of urban settlements in Anbar Governorate

Geographers were interested in studying urban settlements and analyzing their characteristics as they are one of the most important and complex human phenomena, especially as they represent the greatest human achievements and were not limited to the emergence, development and morphology of cities, but were specialized in studying pictures of the geographical distribution of settlements and the patterns they adopt. It

reached (0.013%) urban settlements per 100 km², which reveals the extent of discrepancy between administrative units and the area occupied by these settlements from one region to another .

It is clear from Map (2) the nature of the spatial distribution of urban settlements in Anbar Governorate as it includes (22) urban settlements, and through Table (1) and Map (3) we find that there is a discrepancy in the relative and numerical distribution of the population of urban settlements in Anbar Governorate. The stable of the Fallujah district ranked first, with a percentage of (28.3%), and the second place was stable in the Ramadi district center, with a percentage of (25.25). Settlements (Al-Wafa', Al-Nukhaib, Al-Walid) and their percentages were (0.59, 0.23, 0.03%) respectively, and the reason for this is due to the occurrence of these settlements within the western desert plateau, their distance from surface water sources and from the center of the governorate, and the lack of economic activities that attract the population there.

Map (2)

Spatial distribution of urban settlements according to the districts of Anbar Governorate

Source :Republic of Iraq, Ministry of Water Resources, Directorate of Public Survey, Anbar Administrative Map, 2010, scale .(500,000:1)

Table (1) Distribution of the population of urban settlements in Anbar Governorate, according to the estimates of the year 2021

Sequence	Stable	Population	%
1	Ramadi	235406	25.2
2	Wafa	5567	0.59
3	Habaniya	34005	3.64
4	Heat	70201	7.52
5	Baghdadi	7407	0.79
6	Kabaisa	17921	1.92
7	Furat	3445	0.36
8	Fallujah	264219	28.3
9	Saqlawiyah	10075	1.07
10	Karma	12361	1.32
11	Amriya	25324	2.71
12	Anah	22110	2.36
13	Rawa	19100	2.04
14	Hadithah	48970	5.24
15	Haqlanneya	14874	1.59
16	Barwana	17614	1.88
17	Ratba	29925	3.20
18	Nukhaib	2238	0.23
19	Al-Waleed	315	0.03
20	Qaim	77993	8.35
21	Al-Obour	11788	1.26
22	Obaidi	2359	0.25
Total		933217	%100

Source: Republic of Iraq, Ministry of Planning, Central Statistical Organization, Anbar Governorate Statistics Directorate, population estimates for the year 2020.

Map(3) The numerical distribution of the population of urban settlements in Anbar Governorate, according to the estimates of the year 2021

Source: Table (1).

2-Spatial distribution of urban settlements

The geographical distribution of human settlement centers represents the cornerstone of the study of human settlement, leading to the detection of its distributional patterns. There is no doubt that there is a relationship between the pattern of spread and distribution and its signature factors; The difference in the natural environment in terms of surface, climate and water resources would lead to different spatial values. The person assumes the task of choosing the most appropriate ones for the purpose of his stability and the conduct of his economic activity

The image of the spatial distribution of urban settlement centers in Anbar Governorate did not appear arbitrarily, but there are a number of natural and human factors that played different roles and to varying degrees in determining these features. Reliable data represented in obtaining spatial data with correct geographical coordinates taken by a device (GPS), which represent the real locations of the studied phenomena represented in correct (X,Y) coordinates, and on this basis a database was created for urban settlements that is more useful in identifying and knowing distribution patterns. The spatial location of urban settlements, as follows :

1-Standard Distance Modeling Analysis .

It is one of the most important measures of spatial dispersion that is similar in its concept to the standard deviation, and this method is one of the most prominent measures of spatial dispersal of distributions, and is used to measure the extent of the phenomenon's spread from its adjusted center , and this method was used based on geographic information systems and by (Arc GIS) program and from During the application of (Arc

Toolbox), and after performing some steps, the program draws a circle on the map that represents the standard distance for that distribution. the degree of spread of the spatial distribution; It is clear from map (4) that approximately (70%) of the points representing urban settlements in the governorate are located within the standard distance circle

Map (4) the standard distance to urban settlements in Anbar Governorate

Source: Arc Map program.

-2 Average Nearest Neighbor Analysis.

The nearest neighbor analysis aims to find out the pattern of the spread of a specific geographical phenomenon geographically or spatially, by comparing the actual distribution of the phenomenon with a specific theoretical distribution, which represents the ratio of the measured distance (the average distances from each point of it) divided by the theoretical distance or the expected distance in the case of the pattern randomly for the same number of points and the same surface area on the ground .()

Neighborliness can be extracted using GIS software (ArcGIS) through the (Arc Toolbox) application, then from the toolbox choose the tool (Spatial Statistic Tool) and then (Analyzing Patterns), and then choose the (Average Nearest Neighbor) tool, as it appears to us A window to add the health service layer, and it also contains the path to save the file and then (√) in the box in front of it (optional), then the program creates an illustration of the adjacency.

In order to find out the pattern on which the phenomenon is distributed according to the neighborly relationship, the results of the program’s analysis of the shapes of the point distribution patterns, which range between (2.15-0), and the closer the result is to (0) indicates that the distribution is clustered, and the closer the result is to (2.15). This indicates that the distribution is uniform, while the value (1) indicates the random distribution.

The bottom of the figure shows the confidence levels that range between (0.01-0.10) on the right side, and (-0.01--0.10) on the left side. It also contains (z) values that accompany confidence levels (Critical Values), which are shown in Figure (1) .

It is clear from Figure (2) that the correlation of the neighbor closest to the urban settlements in Anbar Governorate (R) reached (Dispersed), which means that the correlation of the neighbor took the divergent pattern as it approached the value (1.4), and this pattern is consistent with the distribution of urban settlements with the extension of the Euphrates River in Governorate.

Figure (1) Modeling analysis of the nearest-neighbor link pattern on which the phenomenological distribution is located

Source: .Arc GIS; Help; Working; with –Arc GIS; desktop

Figure (2) The pattern of the link of the nearest neighborhood to urban settlements in Anbar Governorate

Source: Arc Map

The urban settlements in Anbar province take the following spatial patterns according to the natural regions of the province:

1-Upper Euphrates Region:

It is clear from map (5) and from the results of the standard distance analysis that the area of the circle is widening despite the fact that most of the settlements are inside the circle, and this is an indication of the divergence of the distribution of urban settlements from their adjusted center. Dispersed regular pattern, which includes the stables of Al-Qaim, Anah, Rawa, Al-Obour, Al-Baghdadi, Hit District Center.

This pattern is consistent with the pattern of population distribution (the linear pattern), where the centers of settlements are arranged in a linear shape that extends along the course of the Euphrates River as a result of the availability of fertile lands that surround the Euphrates River valley, and also that the governorate's climate is characterized as a dry desert climate. The population adopts this pattern, and that the linear pattern is not limited to the course of the Euphrates River. It also appears with the extension of the transportation routes in the province, especially the railways, as many settlements have appeared that extend from Al-Qaim to the Baghdad Governorate.

Map (5) the standard distance to urban settlements in Anbar Governorate

Source: Arc Map program.

Figure (3) The pattern of the link of the closest neighborhood to urban settlements in Anbar Governorate

Source :Arc Map program .

2-Territory of the alluvial plain :

It is clear from map (6) and from the analysis of the results of the standard distance that the percentage of urban settlements within the circle amounted to (22.7%), while the percentage of settlements outside the circle reached (77.3%), and this is an indication of the concentration of the distribution of settlements around its adjusted center. Figure (4) showed that the distribution pattern of the settlements is the clustered pattern, which includes the settlements of Ramadi District, Habbaniyah, Fallujah District, Karma, and Saqlawiyah .

This pattern of distribution is characterized by the convergence and gathering of stability centers within a limited geographical area, which appear in the form of groups close to each other, and this is due to the availability of the main requirements that help human stability and urbanization, as the surface water, which is represented by the Euphrates River and the Saqlawiya stream and its multiple branches, plays a major role in The emergence of such a pattern can be observed in the eastern parts of the province and even the administrative borders with Baghdad province .

3-Scatter pattern

It is clear from map (7) and from the results of the standard distance analysis that the percentage of urban settlements within the circle reached (13.6%), while the percentage of settlements within the circle reached (86.4%), and this is an indication of the divergence of the distribution of urban settlements from their adjusted center .

As for the nearest neighbor, figure (5) showed that the distribution pattern is random, and this pattern appears especially in the western plateau region, which constitutes a large proportion of the governorate, as there is more than one reason for the distribution of urban settlements in a scattered and irregular manner, often Urban centers and cities grow in areas where there are some natural potentials, especially groundwater that appears in the form of wells, springs, and fertile soil, such as the center of Al-Rutba district, the districts of Al-Waleed, Al-Nukhayb, Al-Rahaliyah, and Kubaisa .

Map (6) the standard distance to urban settlements in Anbar Governorate

Source: Arc Map program.

Figure (4)
The pattern of the link of the nearest neighborhood to urban settlements in Anbar Governorate

Source: Arc Map program.

Map (7)
The standard distance to urban settlements in Anbar Governorate

Source :Arc Map program.

Figure (5)
The pattern of the link of the nearest neighborhood to urban settlements in Anbar Governorate

Source :Arc Map program .

3-Urban primacy index modeling analysis

Every city is characterized by natural and human characteristics that distinguish it from other cities, and we do not find two cities that are completely similar in their natural and human characteristics. To see how they are organized into certain patterns and types, this is what distinguishes the personality of each stable society. The geographer can do this by arranging the sizes of cities in descending order, then identifying the pattern taken by

the distribution of cities on the basis of their sizes and revealing the extent of the regularity of this pattern and whether it follows an empirical rule or a law established in this field, which has been studied as follows :

1-The rank size rule :

The American researcher, George K, Zipf, studied a group of American cities and found a relationship between the pattern taken by the order of cities and the number of their inhabitants on the logarithmic distribution scheme. The other in one of the regions, through which it is possible to determine the imbalance in the distribution of population sizes on human settlements in order to restore balance in the size distribution, including balanced development in all economic and social aspects that would reduce the dominance of the center over the rest of the settlements , and the rank rule states - The size of the population of the second city in terms of population size is equal to half (1/2) the size of the population of the first city, and the size of the population of the third city is equal to (1/3) the size of the population of the first city, and the size of the population of the fourth city is equal to (1/4) the size of the population The first city, and so on, to (n) of the cities, the order of which is (1/n), which can be reached through the following mathematical relationship :

$PR = P1R$, where :

PR = Population size of city rank $P1$ = Population size of first city

R =City Rank

It appears through its application to the sizes of urban settlements in Anbar Governorate for the year (2021) and as shown in Table (2) and Figure (6) that there is a significant difference between the real population size and the theoretical size, and it includes all urban settlements except for the first (Fallujah), as The size of the second stable (gray) reached (1/2) the size of the first stable, and the size of the third stable (Al-Qaim) reached (1/3) the size of the first stable, while the lowest size was recorded for the al-Obaidi, al-Nukhayb and al-Walid stables, which indicates a lack of The balance in the size distribution, as the stable (Fallujah) dominates over the rest of the urban settlements in the governorate, and the reason for this is that these urban settlements were suffering from a lack of services and job opportunities, most of which were concentrated in the center of the governorate and the neighboring settlements, which made the population migrate towards the center, so many of the settlements appeared in the lower Hierarchy of urban settlements .

Table(2)
Hierarchical arrangement of urban centers in Anbar Governorate according to the base of rank - size

Sequence	Stable	Population	%	Gap
1	Ramadi	235406	25.2	0
2	Wafa	5567	0.59	103297
3	Habaniya	34005	3.64	-11000
4	Heat	70201	7.52	4147
5	Baghdadi	7407	0.79	-3873
6	Kabaisa	17921	1.92	-10031
7	Furat	3445	0.36	-7820
8	Fallujah	264219	28.3	-7703
9	Saqlawiyah	10075	1.07	-7247
10	Karma	12361	1.32	-7321
11	Amriya	25324	2.71	-6098
12	Anah	22110	2.36	-4404
13	Rawa	19100	2.04	-5450
14	Hadithah	48970	5.24	-6511
15	haqlanneya	14874	1.59	-5826
16	Barwana	17614	1.88	-6438
17	Ratba	29925	3.20	-8135
18	Nukhaib	2238	0.23	-9111
19	Al-Waleed	315	0.03	-10461
20	Qaim	77993	8.35	-10851
21	Al-Obour	11788	1.26	-10343
22	Obaidi	2359	0.25	-11694
Total		933217	%100	232214

Source: Republic of Iraq, Ministry of Planning, Central Statistical Organization, Anbar Governorate Statistics Directorate, population estimates for the year 2020.

It is clear from Table (2) and Map (8) that the analyzes of the inverted rank came with varying results. On the basis of this, urban settlements in Anbar Governorate were classified into six levels :

1-The first level (Al-Waleed, Al-Obaidi, Al-Nukhaib, Al-Baghdadi, Al-Karma, Al-Saqlawiyah, Al-Wafa, Al-Obour, Al-Furat) has a value of $.(0.045 - 0.076)$

2-The second level (Amriya, Kabaisa, Barwana, Anah, Rawa) has a value of $.(0.077 - 0.125)$

3-The third level (ratba ,habaniya) has a value of $.(0.126 - 0.200)$

4-The fourth level (Hadithah, Al-Qaim) has a value of $.(0.333 - 0.201)$

5-The fifth level (Heat, Al-Obaidi) has a value of $.(0.05 - 0.334)$

6-The sixth level (Fallujah, Ramadi) has a value of $.(1 - 0.6)$

As for the arrangement of the governorate's settlements according to the ideal and assumed size, it becomes clear to us from the map (9) the nature of the results of the analysis. The Fallujah stable recorded a population size of (264,219) people, and the Ramadi stable ranked second with a population size of (132109) people, and the Qaim stable ranked third with a population size of (88,993) people, and finally came the settlements of Nukhaib and Al-Walid with a population size of (12,581, 12009) people, respectively .

With regard to the results of modeling the analysis of the difference between the real size and the ideal (assumed) size, it was shown from the map (10) that there is a discrepancy between the urban settlements in Anbar Governorate, where the Ramadi stable recorded the highest value of (103297) people, and the stable Al-Walid ranked second with a size of (11694)) people, and came in the third stable rank, based on a population size of (11,000) people, while the lowest value was recorded by the two stables, Hit and Haditha, with a population size of (4147, 3873) people, respectively, and with regard to the size ratio of the first city, it is clear from the map (11) that it is stable Fallujah recorded the highest percentage (100%) at the real and ideal (assumed) distribution level, while the lowest value was recorded in Al-Waleed stable with a percentage of (0.11%) for the real size and (4.5%) for the ideal (assumed) size .

2-Low of Primate city :

It was brought by Mark Jefferson by studying a group of cities and found that in (18) countries the size of the largest city is three times the city that follows it. The ratio between the first, second, and third city is, respectively, 20:30:100, and the first city has an impact on the neighboring cities in an amount commensurate with the distance from it.

It is clear about the volumetric distribution of urban centers within the urban system, and it shows through this the variation of the volumetric distribution and the extent of its concentration and dispersion between the parts of the study area, and through the application of the law of the first city to the urban centers of Anbar Governorate and through reading and interpretation of Table (3) and Map (12) it becomes clear that there are A large gap between the real size of the city and the rank assumed according to Jefferson's law came in agreement with the first city, which represents the stable of Fallujah, and not in agreement with the other governorate settlements, and from the above it is clear to us that the urban centers In Anbar Governorate, it is consistent with and converges with the rank-size rule, with a relative imbalance in the structure and distribution of urban settlements in the governorate .

Figure (6)

Modeling maps of the hierarchical arrangement of the population size of urban settlements in Anbar Governorate

Map (8) inverted rank Map	(9) arrangement of urban settlements
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Map (10) the difference between the Ideal and the real size Map

(11) the size in relation to the first city

Source: Table (2).

Table (3)
Applying the first city law to urban settlements in Anbar Governorate.

Sequence	Stable	Population	Stable size	Rank
1	Fallujah,	264219	100	100
2	Ramadi	235406	89.09	30
3	Al-Qaim	77993	29.51	20

Source: Republic of Iraq, Ministry of Planning, Central Statistical Organization, Anbar Governorate Statistics Directorate, population estimates for the year 2020.

Map (12) A sample of the results of applying the law of the first city to urban settlements in Anbar Governorate

Source: Table (3).

Conclusions:

1-The research showed that there is a discrepancy in the distribution of the population of urban settlements in Anbar Governorate, as the largest population size of the Fallujah district center reached (264,219) people, while Al-Waleed stable came with the lowest population size of (315) people, which in turn results from the variation in conditions Natural, human and governed by each stable.

2-The research revealed that the centers of urban stability in Anbar Governorate take multiple forms, and this in turn is the result of the control of geographical factors (natural and human) in that distribution, as the scattered (random) distribution pattern appeared in the western plateau, while the settlements extending with the Euphrates River Valley and its plain The flood has taken the divergent (regular) pattern due to the linear extension of human phenomena, while the sedimentary plain settlements have a convergent (convergent) pattern.

3-The use of (the presumption of neighborliness) made it possible to determine the spatial distribution patterns of urban settlements in Anbar Governorate with great accuracy.

Recommendations:

In light of the conclusions reached by the research, the following can be recommended:

1-The necessity of classifying urban settlements in the study area in terms of quantity and quality based on specific criteria that are compatible with planning processes for human stability, in order to increase the efficiency of the sites that will be identified for urban stability centers, which will enable them to perform their tasks and production and service functions.

-2Work to find a comprehensive database that can be used to draw up appropriate development plans for the development and development of those centers in the study area.

3- Motivating the relevant authorities to use geographic information systems (GIS) to study and analyze the spatial distribution and discover the needs of its inhabitants to show us the patterns of spatial distribution, in the light of which these centers can be developed in line with the objectives of the place development.

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